

***AV CLASH* – ONLINE TOOL FOR MIXING AND VISUALIZING AUDIO RETRIEVED FROM *FREESOUND.ORG* DATABASE**

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the project *AV Clash* will be presented. *AV Clash* is a Web-based tool for integrated audiovisual expression, created by Video Jack (the author and André Carrilho, with the assistance of Gokce Taskan). In *AV Clash*, users can manipulate seven “objects” that represent sounds, incorporating audio-reactive animations and graphical user interface elements to control animation and sound. The sounds are retrieved from online sound database *Freesound.org*, while the animations are internal to the project. *AV Clash* addresses the following research question: how to create a tool for integrated audiovisual expression, with customizable content, which is flexible, playful to use and engaging to observe? After an introduction to the project, a contextualization with similar works is presented, followed by a presentation of the motivations behind the project, and past work by Video Jack. Then the project and its functionalities are described. Finally, conclusions are presented, assessing the achievement of the initial aims, and addressing the limitations of the project, while outlining paths for future developments.

1. INTRODUCTION

AV Clash is a Web-based project by Video Jack (the author and André Carrilho, with the assistance of Gokce Taskan), which allows for the creation of audiovisual compositions, consisting of combinations of sound and animation loops. *AV Clash* is composed of seven audiovisual units, which enable playback and manipulation of four different loops of sound and audio-reactive visuals (one combination of audio and visuals at a time). These units were named “Interactive AudioVisual Objects” (“IAVOs”) since they are composed of user interface (UI) elements that trigger and manipulate sounds, together with animations that react to those sounds. The sounds in *AV Clash* are retrieved from *Freesound.org*, an online sound database. The animations were developed by André Carrilho.

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AV Clash is still being developed, and tested, by Video Jack. Therefore it is not online yet, although Video Jack have already registered the domain www.avclash.com, where the project will be hosted. For now, this domain points to a page where demonstration tracks recorded with *AV Clash* can be listened to. No public presentations (performances or exhibitions) have been made with the project yet.

2. CONTEXTUALIZATION

AV Clash follows a long tradition of explorations towards integration of sound and image. Ancient Greek philosophers, such as Aristotle and Pythagoras, considered that there was a correlation between the musical scale and the rainbow spectrum of hues [4]. The color to music correlation was further explored in the Renaissance by several artists, including Leonardo da Vinci, and later by Isaac Newton [9, pp. 45-46]. Newton’s experiments influenced the creation of the *Ocular Harpsichord*, an early “color organ” by Father Louis Bertrand Castel, around 1730 [4].

Wallace Rimington created his electric *Colour Organ* in 1893, which “mixed primary colors into more nuanced hues that could be projected on gently-moving gauzy curtains to obtain polymorphous color flows” [3]. This *Colour Organ* inspired composer Alexander Scriabin to write “a scenario of changing colors into the score of his 1910 Prometheus symphony” [3]. The tradition of color organs continued into the mid 20th century, and influenced abstract filmmakers – “for the cinema, with its standardized methods of production, reproduction and exhibition, seemed the ideal vehicle for Color Music” [3].

In the 1920s, Oskar Fischinger and Walther Ruttmann created “visual music” films in Germany – a combination of tinted animation with live music [4]. Oskar Fischinger moved to Hollywood in 1936, becoming an inspiration to a younger generation of visual music artists, such as Jordan Belson, Harry Smith and brothers John and James Whitney. The Whitney brothers “decided to take up abstract animation after seeing a screening of Oskar's films” [3]. John Whitney is “widely considered ‘the father of computer graphics’” for his explorations of computer-generated visuals through mathematical functions [6, p. 15]. He was among the first generation to use computers for the creation of artworks in the 1960s.

Progress in computing hardware played an important role in the dissemination of digital art from the late 20th century onwards. Sound is one of the major areas of exploration for digital artists. Artistic digital sound and music is a vast territory, that includes: “pure sound art (without any visual component), audio-visual installation environment and software, Internet-based projects that allow for real-time, multi-user compositions and remixes, as well as networked projects that involve public places or nomadic devices” [6, p. 133].

These digital sound and music projects are frequently interactive, and some of them incorporate visuals: “(they) also commonly take the form of interactive installations or ‘sculptures’ that respond to different kinds of user input or translate data into sounds and visuals” [6, p. 136]. Many of these projects that combine music and visuals digitally “stand in the tradition of kinetic light performance or the visual music of the German abstractor and painter Oskar Fischinger” [6, p. 134]. Among the artists that explore integrated audiovisual expression by digital means are: Golan Levin, notably with his *Audiovisual Environment Suite*; Toshio Iwai, with projects such as his recent *Electroplankton* and *Tenori-On*; and John Klima, namely with *Glasbead*, an “online art work that enables up to 20 simultaneous participants to make music collaboratively via a colorful three-dimensional interface” [8, p. 54].

Internet proved to be a fertile territory for developing digital sound and music projects, exploring the possibilities of connecting different musicians, sound artists, and their audiences. In 1998, Sergi Jordà created the first version of *FMOL*, “an Internet-based music composition system that could allow cybercomposers to participate in the creation of the music for La Fura’s next show, F@ust 3.0 (...) freely inspired by Goethe’s work” [2, p. 326]. Like *Glasbead*, it allowed for online collaborative music composition.

*Freesound Radio*¹ (2009) is another example of Web-based sonic collaboration. It is an online “experimental environment that allows users to collectively explore the content in *Freesound.org* by listening to combinations of sounds represented using a graph data structure” [7, p. 1]. *Freesound Radio* retrieves sounds from *Freesound.org*, “one of the most widely used sites for sharing sound files licensed under a Creative Commons (CC) license” [7, p. 1].

3. MOTIVATION AND PREVIOUS WORK

AV Clash is Video Jack’s fourth major interactive audiovisual project, after *Heat Seeker* (2006), *AVOL* (2007) and *Master and Margarita* (2009).

Among previous Video Jack projects, the most direct predecessor of *AV Clash* is *AVOL*². *AVOL* allows for the integrated manipulation of sound and visual elements. The project is composed of seven “objects”, which enable

triggering four possible combinations of sound and visuals. These “objects” integrate graphical user interface elements to manipulate the audiovisual combinations. Objects can be moved around the screen, and object collisions generate special animations and sounds.

After the conclusion of *AVOL* in 2007, and its presentation in several festivals in 2008, the author detected several limitations in the project. Among these limitations are: a fixed number of sound and animation loops; a small degree of audio and visual manipulation possibilities; difficulty in making simultaneous changes in multiple objects; absence of recording or sharing capabilities; difficulties in identifying each object; and lack of collaboration functionalities.

Video Jack started developing a new project in early 2010, entitled *AV Clash*, to address the limitations of *AVOL*. In order to allow for a greater audio flexibility, the author decided to connect this new project to an online sound database. *Freesound.org*, with its vast repository of *Creative Commons* licensed sounds and its tag-based audio categorization, seemed to be adequate. The precedent of *Freesound Radio*, which is successful in retrieving sounds from *Freesound.org* for sonic composition, also pointed out in this direction. The animations would still be developed by Video Jack, but it would be possible for users to choose among a list of different animations associated with a certain tag. The author invited a former student, Gokce Taskan, to collaborate on the programming side of the development. Because of the importance of vector animation for the project, *Freesound Radio*’s successful usage of *Flash*, and the experience gained with previous projects, Video Jack decided to continue using Adobe *Flash* for the development of *AV Clash*.

AV Clash expands on *AVOL*, by addressing the following research question: how to create a tool for integrated audiovisual expression, with customizable content, which is flexible, playful to use and engaging to observe?

4. DESCRIPTION OF THE TOOL

4.1 Image and Sound Association

Each IAVO has a “tag” associated to it, which is retrieved from *Freesound.org*. In a first stage of development, 10 *Freesound.org* tags will be supported, chosen from its most popular tags. *AV Clash* contains seven animations per tag, in a total of 70 animations. The tag of each IAVO acts as a filter to the possible four sounds and four animations it may contain. Each tag is associated with a color. During one *AV Clash* session, the user may change sounds and animations, and even the tag, of each IAVO. More tags and animations will be added in later stages of development.

4.2 Start Screen and Stage

When users enter *AV Clash*, they are presented with a screen composed of seven colored vertical bars, of equal width – the stage. Each bar, colored according to the associated tag, represents a different activation point for

¹ <http://radio.freesound.org/>

² <http://www.videojackstudios.com/projects/avol>

each IAVO. When the project starts, the sounds are loaded from online sound database *Freesound.org*. As the 28 sounds are loading, a circular pre-loader appears near the bottom of the screen, to represent the loading process of the four sounds associated with each IAVO. The name of the tag is shown above the circle. A percentage is shown in the center of the circle, displaying the total loaded percentage of the four sounds.

The selection of initial tags, sounds and animations is random. Seven random tags are selected by the software, and then four random sounds and animations are selected per tag, among the ones associated with that tag. The sounds are not picked among the totality of sounds available per tag, but rather from the 20 most popular sounds with that tag (based on number of downloads from *Freesound.org*).

After all 28 sounds have been loaded, the bars disappear – they split up in two at the point where the pre-loader was, and retracts into the top and bottom edges. The IAVOs appear in the place of the pre-loaders, but they are not playing yet.

The stage is resizable, adapting to changes in the browser size. However, there is a minimum size, beyond which it does not shrink further (800 by 600 pixels).

4.3 “Stopped IAVO” User Interface and Functionalities

When an IAVO is not playing, it shows a limited set of options. If the user is not rolling over the object with the cursor, only an outer “ring” is shown, and a central button, colored according to the object’s tag. This ring allows for the IAVO to be dragged and “thrown” on the stage. When the cursor rolls over the object, additional options are shown: four audiovisual loop selection buttons, and a red button, which deletes the object (Figure 1.). The tag of the object is also shown above the IAVO.

Figure 1. Stopped IAVO, in rollout (left) and rollover (right) states

4.4 “Playing IAVO” User Interface and Functionalities

The UI of each playing IAVO is composed of nine buttons and two sliders (Figure 2.).

Figure 2. UI of playing IAVO, with second sound selected

4.4.1 Presentation of Main UI Elements

The UI is arranged around and inside the IAVO’s “ring”, which allows for dragging and throwing the object around the stage. The ring also incorporates two faders, shaped as semi circles on each of the sides. Inside of the ring are nine buttons, four of which arranged in a two-by-two grid (the “selection buttons”), with four additional buttons in the outside middle points of the grid (red stop button on top, green “solo” button on bottom, cyan audio effect button on the left, and magenta visual effect button on the right), and one more button in its center (the “back” button).

Different UI elements are visible, depending on user interaction and the position of the cursor relatively to the IAVO. In its “passive” state, when the user is not interacting with it, only the outer half of the ring and part of the faders are shown – the fader thumbs are hidden (Figure 3., left). When the user rolls over the outer half of the ring, its inner half appears, and also the fader thumbs (Figure 3., right), allowing for the manipulation of the faders. Rolling over within the inner half of the ring causes the whole UI of the IAVO to appear (Figure 2.), and also the tag of the object, shown above the IAVO.

Figure 3. UI of playing IAVO in "roll out" state (left) and outer ring "roll over" (right)

4.4.2 Buttons and Faders

Pressing one of the selection buttons causes a switch in the audio and animation loops currently playing. The button relative to the audiovisual loop playing is always hidden.

Pressing the red button stops the sound and animation currently playing (the IAVO switches to “stopped” position). The green button “solos” the IAVO, stopping all the remaining ones. When an IAVO is stopped, all its settings (volume, effect selection and setting) are reset.

The center button (colored according to the tag assigned to the IAVO) reveals additional audio and animation selection and manipulation options (the “back” of the object, described below).

Pressing the cyan button modifies the four loop selection buttons, coloring them in cyan. The selection buttons become audio effect selection buttons. There are four audio effects per IAVO: filter, phaser, distortion and delay. The button relative to the selected effect is hidden. Selecting an effect or pressing the cyan button again reverts the selection buttons to white (they become loop selection buttons again). The filter effect is activated by default (Figure 4.).

Figure 4. UI of playing IAVO with audio effects selection buttons (cyan) activated

The magenta button behaves similarly to the cyan button. The selection buttons become magenta, allowing for selection of visual effect. Visual effects determine how the animation of the IAVO reacts to its audio loop. Each animation consists of two parts – one that is audio reactive, and another one that is not. The non-reactive element serves the purpose of making the IAVO always visible, even when the visual effect makes its audio reactive component occasionally disappear. The default visual effect is scale: the size of the animation decreases or increases proportionally to the amplitude of the sound. The remaining behaviors are: opacity (opacity of animations react to sound amplitude); blur (blur level of animations is inversely proportional to the sound amplitude); and RGB transformation (red, green and blue values of the animation are transformed proportionally to sound amplitude).

Independently of the color of the selection buttons, rolling out of the IAVO and rolling in again presents the

loop selection buttons (and not the cyan or magenta effect buttons).

The left fader controls the intensity of the audio effect. Its default value is zero (minimum). The right fader controls the volume of the sound, and the size of the animation (both its reactive and non reactive elements). Its default position is in the middle.

4.5 Dragging, Throwing and Clashes

An IAVO can be dragged and repositioned on the stage. It can also be “thrown”, by dragging and releasing the IAVO in motion. The “throw” behavior causes the IAVO to continue moving in the direction and the speed it had when released, indefinitely, until the user clicks on it again, or presses the “back stage” button. If the IAVO reaches the edges of the screen, it starts moving in the opposite direction, with the same speed.

When a moving IAVO hits another object, a clash animation occurs, and a clash sound is triggered within the static object. The IAVO starts moving in the opposite direction. The collision sound consists of a one second random segment, from one of the four sounds of the static IAVO that is currently not playing (picked randomly), with a delay effect applied to it.

4.6 IAVO User Interface and Functionalities – “Back”

When the user presses the center button of the IAVO, an animation occurs, transforming the UI of the object: the four selection buttons expand into four larger rectangles, and the central button is enlarged and rotated. All the remaining previous UI elements disappear, with the exception of the ring, which still is partially visible underneath the new four rectangles (Figure 5.).

Figure 5. Back of the IAVO, in rollover state

Each of the four new rectangles allows users to pick and adjust sounds and animations for the respective four loop selection buttons of the IAVO. Each rectangle is composed of two elements: a graphical representation of the sound loop, on the top, and an image from the animation, on the bottom. Sliders on top allow for adjusting the start and stop positions for the loop. A slider on the bottom allows for adjusting the reactivity of the animation to the sounds, since some sounds might have a lower dynamic range than others. Moving this “audio reactive sensitivity” slider to the right compensates for a lower sound dynamics. The default position of this slider is center.

By clicking in the sound image, a pop-up menu appears, allowing for the selection of other sounds from *Freesound.org* with the same tag. The pop-up menu includes the following information per sound: file name; short description; duration; author name. The pop-up appears up or down from the point where the user has clicked, depending where there is more space in the screen. When one sound is selected, a pre-loader animation is triggered – a circle starts to be drawn around the ring of the IAVO. When the circle is fully drawn, the sound has finished loading.

Clicking in the animation image activates a pop-up with images and names of other animations associated with that tag. Changes in the sound or image do not produce any immediate change in the current animation or sound playing in that IAVO (unless it occurs in the rectangle relative to the loop that is playing). In the left of the rectangle is a play button, which previews the current selection of sound and image, without closing the “back” of the object. The play button becomes then a stop button.

When the user presses the central button, the “back” of the IAVO is closed, with an animation that mirrors its opening (in reverse). If there were any changes in the sound or animation, within the rectangle relative to the loop that was playing before, these changes will now be reflected. In case the preview had been active previously to closing, that audiovisual loop remains playing. If the IAVO was stopped, it will remain stopped, unless the preview had been active.

4.7 Deleting an IAVO, and Making it Reappear

When an IAVO is stopped, its red button is not longer a stop button, but instead a delete button (as was shown in Figure 1.). When this delete button is pressed, the object disappears, and the correspondent colored bar reappears, in the same position it had in the start of the application.

This reappearance occurs with an animation: the bar appears from the top and bottom edges of the stage. By clicking anywhere in this bar, the bar disappears again, and the IAVO reappears in that point (stopped). The bar disappears into the top and bottom edges of the screen by splitting in two at the point where the user has clicked (Figure 6.).

Figure 6. Stage with four active bars, representing four deleted IAVOs

4.8 “Back Stage”

In the upper right corner of the stage, there is a “back stage” button. Activating the “back stage” option allows for introducing changes to multiple objects in the same screen, and also for changing the tag of each IAVO (Figure 7.).

Figure 7. “Back stage” of *AV Clash*

Pressing the “back stage” button triggers a series of events. The “back stage” button becomes a “stage” button. If any object had its “back” visible, it will be closed first. All IAVOs move back to the area of their original bar, aligned vertically to the same position, near the bottom of the stage. All bars of active IAVOs reappear by expanding from the top and bottom of the stage to the vertical position of the IAVO, but do not close completely, stopping at the edge of its ring. Regarding the IAVOs that were not active, their bars open slightly, revealing their ring (aligned vertically with the remaining objects). Immediately after, all IAVOs reveal their “back”, with the same animation described above. One more element is shown in this animation: a tag button appears above the objects, sliding from behind them. The sounds and animations that were playing previously continue to play. Two black bars appear on top and in the bottom of the screen. The top bar reveals load and save

options, while the bottom bar shows the credits of the project.

Now users can change all animations and sounds of all IAVOs, similarly to how they could change the “back” of each IAVO individually. Additionally, users can change tags. By pressing the tag button that is now on top of each IAVO, a pop-up appears with a list of tags. (Figure 8.)

Figure 8. "Back stage" with several pop-ups open

A change in tag loads four new sounds from *Freesound.org*, chosen randomly among the 20 most popular ones with that tag. A pre-loader animation then takes place, similar to the circular initial pre-loader, and the sound change pre-loader (overlapped with the IAVO). When the loading process concludes, all sounds and animations of the IAVO are replaced. The IAVO reverts to its defaults, and if any sound or animation was playing, it is stopped. The bars disappear, mirroring the start of the project.

The “Save Set” button generates a file storing all the options for each IAVO: tag and list of the four sounds and animations; volume and effect level information; and audio and visual effect. The “Load Set” button loads a previously recorded file, consequently changing all the information of each IAVO, and loading new sounds.

5. REFLECTIONS ON THE INTERACTION DESIGN OF *AV CLASH*

In *AV Clash*, only the most relevant UI elements are visible at a given time. Since IAVOs contain a large amount of buttons and interactive elements, they are shown and hidden depending on the position of the mouse relative to the IAVO, and if the IAVO is playing or not. For example, rolling over the ring of a playing IAVO reveals the interactive possibilities contained in the ring, previously hidden (volume and effect fader thumbs, enlarged ring for dragging and throwing). If the user moves the cursor further towards the inside of the ring, more interface options appear (playback and effects buttons). Donald Norman classifies this approach as modularization - creating separate functional modules, “each with a limited set of controls, each specialized for some different aspects of the task” [5, p. 174].

Visibility is important not only for modularity, but also to hide irrelevant options in a certain context. For example, if an IAVO is not playing, the volume and effect faders are hidden. As Donald Norman states, “a good designer makes sure that appropriate actions are perceptible and inappropriate ones invisible” [5, p. xii].

This hiding and showing of elements also indicates feedback, sending users “information about what action has actually been done, what result has been accomplished” [5, p. 27]. Another example of this principle occurs when users press one of the playback selection buttons – the button becomes invisible.

The graphic design of interactive elements in *AV Clash* is meant to convey its functionality. An example of this approach is the design of the ring, which has a jagged appearance, meant to reflect its “draggable” affordance. According to Norman, affordances refer to “the perceived and actual properties of the thing, particularly those fundamental properties that determine just how the thing could possibly be used” [5, p. 9].

The notion of mapping, meaning the relationship between the controls and the results [5, p. 23], is also explored in *AV Clash*. An example of this is the mapping of each IAVO to a specific screen area in the beginning of the session, to which it returns to when users press the “back stage” option. Mappings are also implemented when a playback selection button expands to a full audio and visual loop selection interface – the audio and visual loop selection options are located in the same quadrant of the correspondent selection button.

Besides an emphasis on functionality, the UI of *AV Clash* also references its own aesthetic universe, connected to the circular nature of the animations. These animations, although abstract, are often inspired by concentric “real” objects such as flowers, planets, biological and molecular/atomic structures. The visual appeal of the UI is meant to induce playfulness: “the mouse and the pen-based interface allow the user the immediacy of touching, dragging, and manipulating visually attractive interfaces” [1, p. 23].

6. CONCLUSIONS

6.1 Assessment Regarding Initial Aims

The author considers that *AV Clash* has fulfilled the objective of developing the structure behind *AVOL* into a more flexible project, in terms of source sounds (imported from *Freesound.org*), animations (although less diverse than the sounds) and audiovisual manipulation (through the implementation of sonic and visual effects). The introduction of the “throw” behavior and the development of the “clash” behavior contributed to a higher degree of playfulness. The use of colors and tags (imported from *Freesound.org*) to identify IAVOs also facilitates recognition of objects. The colored bars create a higher visual diversity on the stage. The “save set” functionality introduces an option to save all settings for all IAVOs, allowing for the storing and sharing of user op-

tions. Besides loading new sounds, the “load set” button can quickly change multiple parameters within a session.

However, several limitations have been identified by the author in the project, which should be addressed in a future project, or in a new version of *AV Clash*.

6.2 Paths for future developments

AV Clash could benefit from accessing more content, and from having more content manipulation capabilities. The visual diversity of *AV Clash* is still small compared to its audio side. A database for visuals (possibly vector based animations) could be created, which would then be used by *AV Clash* similarly to *Freesound.org* for sound. Further audio and visual effects could be added. Specific tags for *AV Clash* could be created in *Freesound.org* to ensure coherence of results.

Recording capabilities could be built in *AV Clash*, in order to allow users to record their sessions. Content sharing could also be implemented, not only of sets but also of those recording sessions. This content sharing could also integrate with profiles of users in *Freesound.org*.

Collaboration functionalities could also be implemented. Users could be allowed to take control of a certain IAVO, and play with it. The different users would “jam” together, each with his/her own IAVO. This system would resemble how a band plays in a “real life” stage.

A “sequence” mode could be implemented in *AV Clash*, which would not simply playback one of the sounds of each IAVO, but instead run through the four sounds – in a linear sequence; randomly; or in another sequence defined by the user (for example, by drawing a path in the “back” of the object connecting the four sounds, thus specifying the order). This “sequence” mode is inspired by *Freesound Radio*.

6.3 Final Reflections

These conclusions are preliminary. *AV Clash* is under development, as mentioned before, and is being tested by Video Jack. Therefore it is not online yet, and no public presentations have been done. Video Jack intend to release *AV Clash* online soon, in July 2010. They wish to start presenting the project shortly after, as installation and performance. A domain name has been registered for the project.³ Currently it only displays a few preliminary recordings using a prototype version of the project.

Feedback gathered from users after releasing *AV Clash*, and from presentations, will enrich the conclusions presented in this paper. The author intends to conduct interviews to users, to better assess these conclusions.

The author believes that there is a vast potential for the type of application that *AV Clash* represents – a playful tool for integrated audiovisual expression, which gathers audiovisual resources from Internet repositories, and that

explores the potential of connecting users through the Web via their creativity.

7. REFERENCES

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³ <http://www.avclash.com>